

A novel approach to integrate cold energy storage in a vapour compression cycle

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ABSTRACT

Most renewable energies are intermittent and need to be coupled with energy storage systems. Thermal energy storage units are best suited for short-term storage in a vapour compression cycle. In this study, a thermosiphon cold storage accumulator was designed to address these challenges. The technology presented here is versatile and can be plugged into any vapour compression cycle. The accumulator uses a phase-change material to store and release cold energy during the charging and discharging phases. The process uses the thermosiphon effect to deliver cold energy to the evaporator without using a pump. A laboratory prototype was developed and integrated into a closed refrigerated display cabinet. When the compressor was shut down, the accumulator was able to reduce the air temperature raise in the cabinet to about 4 °C compared to 13 °C without the accumulator.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Cold storage, Thermosiphon, Display cabinet, PCM, Energy Efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main challenges for industrialised countries is to reduce GHG emissions. Supermarkets account for about 4 % of global electricity consumption. 50 % of this is due to refrigeration systems (Alzuwaid et al., 2015). In addition to high electricity consumption, these systems face problems with product temperature uniformity and temperature rise due to defrosting and power failures. As a result, some products may exceed the regulatory storage temperatures, thereby jeopardising food safety (Derens et al., 2006). Optimising these systems through the implementation of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) is a solution. PCMs are materials that can store heat/cold by changing phase and release this energy during the discharging phase by also changing phase. (Ahmed et al., 2010) incorporated a PCM (paraffin; 5 °C) into the wall insulation systems of a refrigerated truck and observed that this resulted in a 16.3 % decrease in heat transfer and a reduction in temperature fluctuations. (Azzouz et al., 2009) placed PCM (water; 0 °C) on the back of the evaporator of a domestic refrigerator giving it 5-6 h of continuous operation without electricity compared to 1-3 h without PCM. (Maiorino et al., 2019) also used water as PCM placed at the top and bottom of each shelf of a domestic refrigerator. They concluded that PCM promoted a better temperature distribution with a temperature difference between two shelves of 0.2 °C with PCM compared to 3.1 °C without PCM. (Alzuwaid et al., 2015) placed PCM (water gel; -2 °C) in the back pipes of an open-door refrigerated display cabinet. They observed a reduction in the maximum air temperature by 2 °C, a decrease in compressor running time and a homogenisation of the product temperature. (Ben-Abdallah et al., 2019) also integrated a PCM (water; 0 °C) into an open-door display cabinet. They observed that the addition of the heat exchanger in the rear duct increased the air velocity at the first and second shelves and decreased the air velocities at the fourth and fifth shelves and the discharge air grid (-28 % air curtain flow rate). As a result, the temperatures of the products on the fifth shelf and at the front (except for the first shelf) were higher than the temperatures of the products in the display cabinet without PCM. During 2 hours of compressor downtime, the temperature of the products increased by only 1 °C with PCM compared to 2 °C without PCM. This paper investigates the

use of a cold accumulator technology with no impact on the airflow of the refrigeration system and which can be plugged into any vapour compression cycle. A prototype was integrated and tested in a closed refrigerated display cabinet.

2. TECHNOLOGY DESCRIPTION AND INTEGRATION

2.1. Cold storage accumulator technology

A typical vapour compression cycle is a loop consisting of an expansion valve, an evaporator, a compressor and a condenser. A refrigerant flows through the loop and undergoes numerous compression and expansion cycles. The evaporator is where the cold is created. For efficient heat transfer, the PCM should be nearly in contact with the refrigerant. Most of the current thermal storage units use a secondary fluid, which implies two levels of heat exchanger and increases the temperature difference, which decreases the thermodynamic efficiency and increases the energy consumption. Some authors have considered placing the PCM in contact (at the back) with the evaporator or integrating it directly (inside) into the evaporator. However, there is no control over the charging/discharging periods of the PCM due to compressor shutdown cycles. When these technologies are inserted inside a refrigerated cabinet, the quantity of PCM is also often limited by the space available. To control the charging and discharging phases and have a good heat transfer, the phase change material has been placed in a finned tube heat exchanger called here accumulator. In this accumulator, there is a nearly direct heat transfer between the PCM and the refrigerant only separated here by a copper wall. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Illustration of the accumulator filled with PCM (liquid state)

The accumulator is integrated into the vapour compression cycle and is placed at the inlet of the evaporator. The storage and release of cold energy are based on the thermosiphon principle, which allows the refrigerant to flow by gravity. The height difference between the accumulator and the evaporator, the phase change temperature and the design of the heat exchangers/loops are key factors in improving charging and discharging efficiencies. Indeed, a significant height difference (about 1 m) between the evaporator and the accumulator is necessary to allow the thermosiphon effect. A system of controllable valves is used to control the charging and discharging times of the PCM. Figure 2.a shows the arrangement used to integrate the cold accumulator into the conventional vapour compression cycle. Figure 2.b shows the accumulator charging phase, and Figure 2.c shows the discharging phase, which uses the thermosiphon principle.

During the charging process, valves 1 and 3 are closed and valves 2 and 4 are open. After leaving the expansion valve, the refrigerant enters the accumulator and transfers the cold energy to the PCM, which drops in temperature and solidifies (Figure 2.b). When the PCM is completely solid, the refrigerant transfers all the cold to the evaporator. When the compressor is stopped (discharging phase), valves 1, 2 and 4 are closed while valve 3 is open: a closed circuit between the evaporator and the accumulator is created. The refrigerant absorbs heat from the products to be cooled and then evaporates. Due to the difference in pressure between the two heat exchangers, the vapour rises naturally in the accumulator. The cold energy stored in the PCM is then returned to the refrigerant which condenses. The liquid then flows back to the evaporator by gravity forces due to the height difference. (Figure 2.c)

This technology can provide cold without the need for a pump. It also offers the possibility of using more easily intermittent renewable energy and preserves food longer in case of compressor failure.

Figure 2: Diagram of the cold storage accumulator integrated into a vapour compression cycle (a) during the charging phase (b) and discharging phase (c)

2.2. Integration of the technology in a display cabinet

The cold storage accumulator (90 cm x 9 cm x 22.5 cm) was integrated into a closed vertical refrigerated display cabinet (2000 mm high, 1340 mm long and 670 m wide) (Figure 3). The accumulator was connected to the original refrigeration system of the display cabinet and was placed, outside, in the upper rear part of the cabinet, as shown in Figure 3.b. This configuration gives more space (exchange surface) to the evaporator, which makes it possible to increase the evaporation temperature. The PCM used is a paraffin mixture (-4 °C), and the accumulator was perfectly insulated to avoid any heat transfer with the surrounding environment.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

An experimental study was conducted to validate the technology. In this study, the behaviour of the display cabinet with and without the thermosiphon cold storage accumulator is compared.

3.1. Instrumentation

To evaluate the thermal behaviour of the display cabinet, the temperature of the air and products in the cabinet as well as the energy consumption need to be measured. The display cabinet and the accumulator were instrumented with T-type thermocouples (accuracy 0.3 °C). Fourteen (14) temperature sensors were positioned to measure the air temperature in the rear duct, on shelves, at the discharge grid and air curtain (Figure 4.a). Eight (8) temperature sensors measured the surface and core temperature of the products

(Figure 4.b). Five (5) sensors were placed in the accumulator to measure the temperature of the PCM at different points (Figure 4.c). Two (2) other sensors were placed to measure the temperature of the refrigerant at the inlet and outlet of the accumulator (Figure 4.c). Methylcellulose packages were used as products.

Figure 3: (a) Diagram of a closed display cabinet; (b) Illustration of the closed display cabinet used; (c) Position of the accumulator in the tested closed display cabinet

Figure 4: Arrangement of thermocouples for (a) air temperature measurements; (b) product temperature measurements; (c) PCM and refrigerant temperature measurements

The refrigerating system of the display cabinet was also instrumented. One (1) thermocouple was placed at the compressor inlet, one (1) at the compressor outlet and one (1) at the condenser outlet. One (1) pressure sensor was placed at the compressor inlet and one (1) at the compressor outlet. A wattmeter was installed

to measure the total power consumed by the whole display cabinet: fan, compressor, lighting, etc. The ambient temperature was also measured.

3.2. Test protocol

An initial experiment was conducted to evaluate the air temperature variation during a one-hour compressor shutdown (demand-side management) with and without the accumulator. The room temperature was set at 21 °C, and the display cabinet was empty. A set of experiments (four in total) was then carried out to estimate the energy consumption of the cabinet with and without the cold accumulator. Two tests were performed with a product loading rate of 50 % and two with a product loading rate of 90 %. The cabinet was operated with and without the cold accumulator for 24 hours for each product loading percentage. The ambient and thermostat temperatures were set at 19 °C and -3 °C, respectively. During the tests with the accumulator, the compressor was shut down twice for an hour and a half.

The cabinet doors were kept closed during all the experiments. Tests are still in progress to assess the impact of other parameters, such as door opening, ambient temperature, and thermostat temperature, on the performance of the accumulator.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the changes in air temperature in the cabinet and at the air curtain, respectively. The impact of the accumulator discharge on the air temperature can be clearly seen.

According to the graphs, the air temperature at the shelves increases slowly during compressor shutdown when there is a discharge of PCM, reaching around 4 °C. In contrast, it increases very quickly if there is no discharge (reaching around 13 °C). This is because, during discharge, the PCM delivers the cold energy stored to the refrigerant circulating between the evaporator and the accumulator due to thermosiphon, thus providing a cooling effect to the cabinet. If there is no discharge (no cold accumulator), no cooling is provided, and heat builds up in the cabinet, causing the air temperature to rise very quickly. It should be noted here that when there are no products in the cabinet, the air temperature rises much faster in both cases because there is no thermal inertia.

Figure 5. Evolution of the air temperature in the display cabinet

Figure 6. Evolution of the air temperature at the air curtain

Table 1 shows the results for the second experience performed with products inside the cabinet. The objective was to have a primary idea of the energy consumption of the cabinet with and without the accumulator.

Table 1. Display cabinet energy consumption with and without the cold accumulator

Ambient temperature (°C)	Thermostat temperature (°C)	Mode	Product loading (%)	Energy consumption over 24h (kWh)	Reduction (%)
19	-3	normal	50	8.14	
19	-3	with DSM	50	7.29	10%
19	-3	normal	90	8.65	
19	-3	with DSM	90	8.34	4%

Tests with DSM (Demand-side Management) are those carried out in the presence of the cold accumulator. For the same parameters (ambient temperature, thermostat temperature, product loading %), operating the display cabinet with the cold accumulator appears to consume less energy than without the accumulator. A 10 % and 4 % reduction in energy consumption is observed for 50 % and 90 % product loading, respectively. These preliminary results seem to show that the accumulator can cool the cabinet while reducing energy consumption. However, further tests must be performed to confirm these findings and improve the accumulator's performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The integration of phase change materials into refrigeration systems can improve their performance and thus reduce GHG emissions by facilitating the use of intermittent renewable energy sources. A new cold storage technology using PCM has been successfully developed. This technology uses the thermosiphon effect to store and restore cold during compressor downtime. The accumulator can be plugged into any vapour compression cycle. Experimental results have shown that discharging the accumulator significantly reduces the temperature rise of the air in the cabinet. This technology enables demand-side management (DSM) as well as the use of renewable energies. Further tests will be carried out where the impact of ambient temperature, product load, thermostat temperature and door opening on the performance of the display cabinet, with and without the accumulator, will be studied. The charging and discharging time, as well as the temperature rise of the products when the compressor is switched off, will also be studied.

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